

THE DEPENDENCE OF THE METHOD OF CULTIVATION OF KISHMISHBOP VARIETIES OF GRAPES ON THE YIELD OF GRAPES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10065827>

Abstract. When the effect of cultivation of kishmishbop varieties of grapes by the ertou method on the grape head and grape yield was studied, the highest indicator compared to the control option was found to be 121.8 t/ha in the kishmish sagdiana variety, the lowest productivity indicator was 14.4 t/ha in the bishmish belyy variety compared to the control option. returned.

Key words: raisin, grape head, crop, productivity, vine bush, fairy tale, tiksimbagaz, mechanical composition.

Enter. Researches on the development of the most optimal standards for the methods of planting grapes, which allow to increase the yield of young varieties of grapes, and on the issues of growing high and quality crops based on them, are carried out in prestigious research centers and institutions in the world, including the Viticulture and Enology Research Center (USA, California), Research Institute of Horticulture, Viticulture and Winemaking (Georgia), Instituto Nacional de Tecnología Agropecuaria (Argentina), Research Institute of Viticulture, Winemaking and Fruit crops (Armenia), Hochschule Geisenheim University (Germany), Viticole et Oenologique (France), Viticultural Research Institute Manisa (Turkey), North Caucasus Research Institute of Horticulture and Viticulture, Russia), Research Institute of Horticulture, Viticulture and Winery named after Academician M. Mirzaev and Research Institute of Plant Science (Uzbekistan).

In order to increase the volume of grape production and export potential, scientific research is being carried out in the following priority directions in the foreign countries that are leading in grape growing today: selection of high-growing kishmishbop varieties of grapes, improvement of the agrotechnical system for each variety, intensive cultivation technologies are being developed. One of the main factors of obtaining a high and quality harvest from Kishmishbop grape varieties is its dependence on the variety. The quality of the harvest and the chemical composition of the grape heads also depend on the biological characteristics of the varieties and the cultivation technologies [1,7].

The location of the experiment. Scientific research will be carried out in 2021-2023 at Gulistan State University "Agricultural Product Processing Technologies" department and "Faizullo Grapes" farm, established in 2005, located in Payariq district of Samarkand region. The total area of the farm is 10 hectares, of which 5 hectares of vines are cultivated by the "Er Tok" method, and 5 hectares are grown by the vertical symbagaz method.

Research methods. The experiments were developed by Kh.Ch.Boriev, N.Sh.Enileev and others "Methodology of calculations and phenological observations in conducting experiments with fruit and berry-bearing plants" [2], "Metody botanicheskogo opisania i agrobiologicheskogo izucheniya sortov vinograda" by M.A. Lazarevskiy [4], recommendations and methods

presented in the methodological literature of N.N. Prostoserdov "Izuchenie vinograda dlya opredeleniya ego ispolzovaniya" [6], "Metodika uchotov i nablyudeniye v opytax s plodovymi i yagodnymi kulturami" [5] by V.F.Moiseychenko held on

Statistical analysis of research results was calculated in Excel 2010 and Statistica 7.0 for Windows computer programs with a confidence interval of 0.95% according to the method shown by B.A. Dospekhov [3].

The results of the research showed that when the Kishmishbop varieties of grapes were grown in the traditional way, in the Kishmish chernyy (control) variety, the number of grape heads per bush was 35.2, the weight of the vine was 280.2 g, the average yield per bush was 9.8 kg, and the total yield was 108.8 t/ha. was determined to be It was reported that the number of vines per bush is 3.5 more, the weight of the vine is 60.4 g less, the average yield per bush is 1.3 kg less than the control option, and the yield per hectare is 14.4 t/ha. The Kishmish Sogdiana variety of grapes had the following parameters compared to the control variant, the number of grapes per bush was 11.8 more than the control variant, the average weight of the grape head was 160.3 g, the average yield of the bush was 10.9 kg more and the yield was 120.1 ts/ha. was observed to be In the F1 white raisin variety, the number of vines per bush is 4.0 more than the control variant, the average weight of the vine is 39.8 g less, the average yield per bush is 0.2 kg less, and the total yield is 2.2 t/ha less.

Mechanical composition and weight of grape heads of different varieties of grapes

№	Options	In the bush number of grape heads, pcs	Average weight of grape head, g	Find out average yield, kg	Productivity, ts/ha
When vine bushes are grown in a fairy tale way					
1	Кишмиш черный (назорат)	35,2± 1,0	280,5± 4,3	9,8	108,8
2	Кишмиш белый	38,7± 1,2	220,1± 10,3	8,5	94,4
3	Кишмиш Согдиана	47,0± 1,2	440,8± 7,4	20,7	229,9
4	Ф1 оқ кишмиш	39,2± 1,3	245,7± 4,4	9,6	106,6
5	Ф1 пушти кишмиш	38,2± 1,4	230,4± 4,5	8,8	97,7
6	Ф1 қора кишмиш	37,2± 1,4	330,4± 4,5	12,2	135,5

In the F1 pink raisin variety, the number of vines per bush is 3.0 more than the control variant, the average weight of the vine is 50.1 g less, the average yield per bush is 1.0 kg less, and the total yield is 11.1 t/ha less.

It was found that in the F1 black currant variety, the number of vines per bush is 2.0 more than the control variant, the average weight of the vine is 49.6 g more, the average yield per bush is 2.4 kg more, and the total yield is 27.7 t/ha.

The following indicators were obtained from the research results. the best productivity when growing vine bushes in the traditional way is 229.9 ts in the Kishmish Sogdiana variety and . F1 black currant variety was found to have a yield of 135.5 ts.

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